

Ion-exchange Equilibrium Studies with Iodate Ion in Mixed Aqueous Alcohols

RADHA TOMAR* and R. P. BHATNAGAR

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

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Iodate, along with other halates, has been studied in aqueous¹ and aqueous acetone^{2,3} solutions. In the present communication, aqueous alcohols have been used for the equilibrium studies of iodate ion against the anion exchanger in nitrate form.

Experimental

Iodate ion was used from the stock solution (0.25 M) which was prepared from its potassium salt (E. Merck, Pro-analysis) in double-distilled water. Methanol (AnalaR), absolute ethanol (Bengal Chemicals) and isopropanol (AnalaR) were used as organic solvents. Amberlite IRA-400 (Cl⁻) converted to its nitrate form, was used as air-dried resin (cap. 3.5 mmol g⁻¹; 40–60 mesh).

Batch technique was used for all equilibrium studies. Apparent selectivity coefficient (K') was calculated as per the method of Kressman and Kitchener⁵. The corrected selectivity coefficients

were computed by using the expression,

$$\ln K = \int_{X_{BR}=0}^{X_{BR}=1} \ln K' dX_{BR}$$

All plots with respect to (1+log K) vs percentage alcohol were straight lines at all ionic concentrations. To see the effect of dielectric constant, the plots of (1+log K) vs $1/\epsilon$ were straight lines (plots omitted).

The effect of resin quantity in gms and comparison of OH⁻ and NO₃⁻ forms of the resin have been seen on selectivity coefficients in aqueous methanol solutions only. Two different mesh sizes (20–40 and 40–60 mesh) of resin were used to their effect on selectivity coefficients.

The selectivity of the iodate ion increased with the amount of the resin. The exchange was facilitated by NO₃⁻ form of the resin. The finer particles of the resin (40–60 mesh) proved as better exchanger for iodate as compared to the coarser form of the resin (20–40 mesh).

Results and Discussion

The results show the increase in exchange of iodate ion against nitrate form of the anion-exchanger with increase of alcohol percentage. Increase in alcohol in water decreases its dielectric constant progressively. Consequently, the potassium salt of the iodate is expected to decrease in its ionisation providing less of iodate ions for exchange purposes. Davydov⁴ showed that dielectric permeability of the solvent influences the solubility, dissociation and association of ions in an electrolyte. In other words, the behaviour of ions in solution will modify due to the dielectric changes. With sufficiently low ionic concentrations, the influence of possible formation of associates and double ions can be excluded in the present work. It is, therefore, the solubility and the dissociation of the electrolyte that appear to be important in the exchange under study. This is influenced by changing the dielectric of the solvent systems used. As it has been seen that increase in percentage of alcohol increases exchange, the same is expected when the dielectric constant decreases or $1/\epsilon$ increases. This has been actually seen in the present studies also. Thus any reasoning which satisfies the need of explaining the increase in exchange with increase in the organic solvent in the aqueous system, can also be the reason for explaining the effect of dielectric constant.

It has been regarded to be the water structure enforced exchange of iodate ion in aqueous and aqueous acetone media². The same is true for aqueous alcoholic solvent systems as well. The resin phase is expected to contain more structured water in the outside solution. This is the reason for the iodate ion showing an increase in exchange with increasing alcohol percentage or increasing $1/\epsilon$.

The other observation are the natural outcome of such media. The increase in quantity increases the exchange as more exchangeable NO_3^- ions are made available for the purpose. It is an observed fact that better exchange has been found in the nitrate form of the resin than the hydroxyl form in aqueous methanol for iodate exchange. The finer particles of the resin give greater surface area and therefore, a better exchange for iodate ion.

References

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